

Collision detection for collaborative assembly operations on high-payload robots

Konstantinos Katsampiris-Salgado^a, Kevin Haninger^b, Christos Gkrizis^a, Nikos Dimitropoulos^a, Jörg Krüger^b, George Michalos^a, Sotiris Makris^{a,*}

^a Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems and Automation, University of Patras, Patras 26504, Greece

^b Department of Automation, Fraunhofer Institute for Production Systems and Design Technology, Pascalstraße 8-9, Berlin 10587, Federal Republic of Germany

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ABSTRACT

Human-robot collaboration for high-payload industrial applications has the potential to unlock new applications and improve operator ergonomics. However, ensuring safety with closer proximity remains challenging due to the large payload. Collision detection can improve safety, but must be modified to consider the dynamics of high payload applications (internal oscillation, effective low-pass filtering of external force), while the higher inertia raises questions about the resulting collision forces. This paper proposes the first collision detection approach for high-payload applications, using a force/torque sensor at the end-effector and motor current measurements for redundancy to be compliant with ISO/TS 15066:2016. Analysis of a linear model informs the design of the detection algorithm and effect of higher payload. Experimental validation shows feasibility and performance of collision detection over a range of motion and payload conditions, and the impact of the safety system in improving an industrial use-case.

1. Introduction

Seamless Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) has the potential to improve both flexibility and reconfigurability of production systems, towards producing customized products of varying lot sizes [1]. An HRC solution can utilize the advantages of the robot's precise motion execution and weight lifting capability, combined with humans' flexible and dexterous nature [2]. Safety remains a critical bottleneck of HRC, especially with closer human-robot proximity, higher payloads, or higher robot speed [3]. Typical approaches to safety in HRC are well-researched [4,5], also with a special focus on industrial applications [6].

While many HRC applications can avoid human-robot proximity, a range of tasks require it, for example when the robot acts as a workpiece-holder [7]. In this case, the robot must be designed for safe contact, where standard design recommendations are the reduction of the inertia of the robot, the prevention/covering of sharp edges and the reduction of contact stiffness [8].

These recommendations cannot be completely followed in high-payload applications. In such cases, a larger, stronger robot kinematic structure is required, which has a higher inertia. While the kinematic

itself and the end-effector can be made safer through the use of a soft sensitive skin, the payload might not be, which can present a hard or sharp object with increased collision risk.

Safety can be improved with collision detection [9,10], but the high payload also limits the utility of classical collision detection methods. These methods can often detect collisions at arbitrary locations on the robot [10], but they are typically designed and tested on cobots with little to no payload [11,12]. A larger robot, typically with higher gear-ratio motors, introduces challenges due to a higher torque drive-train, from increased gearbox friction, higher cogging and torque ripple effects, limiting sensitivity to external force. At the same time, the safety requirements are tighter due to higher inertia. The payload introduces not only gravitational load, but may have dynamics of its own, i.e., significant oscillation at a lower frequency [13], which may falsely trigger a collision detection.

This paper addresses a gap in physical safety on high-payload collaborative robots through collision detection, presenting the first study on a high-payload robot. The novelty of this paper lays in the utilization of an end-effector force/torque (F/T) sensor and joint-space motor torque measurements for a redundant collision detector, analysis of high-payload effects, and experimental validation which

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: makris@lms.mech.upatras.gr (S. Makris).

identifies critical aspects of high-payload collision scenarios. First, the requirements, contact model, and detector are introduced. Next, the contact model is used to analyse high-payload effects on the detector. Finally, the approach is validated experimentally on a high-payload robot, showing the relative impact of robot pose, detection method, and stop category on peak and steady-state collision force.

2. Relevant work

Since the collision detection problem has been in the research and industry for many decades, a lot of approaches have been standardized and their limits have come clear. Initially a sequence of phases for a successful collision detection is proposed [10]. Sensor-less implementations, that are based on the dynamic effect of a contact force have been extensively studied. Such forces can be detected as anomalies in the behaviour of the joints dynamic model [9]. Despite their low accuracy on fast collisions with stiff environments, sensor-less solutions provide a low computational burden, cost-effective way to detect collision in certain conditions.

Another issue that has been studied thoroughly in the past years is the classification of such forces between intentional interaction between the operator or the environment and an unintended collision. To address the aforementioned problem additional external sensors were added. Vision sensors, force load cells, pressure sensitive skins and deterministic models have been developed to inform the detection model that a contact force is anticipated. The only constant on all the above implementation is the dynamic model of the robot, hence the main factor for the limitations on the above approaches derives from the accuracy of the model [12].

Methods of developing a reliable dynamic model include gravity forces identification and internal friction forces and torques estimations. With a more precise model, developed algorithms are better on distinguishing the classes of a detection (intentional or accidental), either with torque sensors [11] or with estimations on the external torques based on the model [15], enabling a seamless HRI when certain criteria are met. Non-model-based approaches, despite their potential suitability for industrial applications due to their software's ability to work independently of specific robot models, have received limited research attention [21]. This independence allows for a high degree of adaptability to various types of manipulators and diverse industrial tasks.

With the rise of computational power and artificial intelligence, the research community approached the problem with machine learning. Data-driven modelling of sensor equipped robots in parallel with neural networks have been developed to quantify the certainty of a classification into safe assumptions or uncertainty. Eliminating the need of sensors, predictive models have been proposed to estimate the current and torques of each joint with satisfactory precision compared to measured robot data [16]. Even though the results of such implementations are promising and open new paths for research, but the lack of the required redundancy for safety-critical sensing presents an obstacle for the development of a model that can be used in the industry. An improved validation method for collision detection, extrapolating a free-space collision from a collision with a fixed Force/Torque sensor, has been tested [17].

In the last years, collaborative robots equipped with collision detection have been commercially available for payloads for as high as 20 kg (the UR20), but for higher payload robots, such feature is not available. The presented methods have limited adaption on high payload robots, since the inertia characteristics have a great influence on the dynamic model, impeding the accuracy needed for an application due to over/under sensitivity.

Summarizing, while numerous collision detection approaches have been materialized, a distinct gap remains for high-payload robots. The methods described largely focus on smaller robots, where the dynamics are relatively straightforward. As weight increases, the robot's inertia starts to play a more significant role, making traditional models less

reliable. Our work fills this gap by not just proposing a collision detection method tailored for high-payload robots, but by also integrating dual sensor and control pipelines: one from the end-effector F/T sensor and another from motor currents. This redundancy does not just enhance reliability but also aligns with critical international safety standards. In essence, while previous studies have set the foundation, our work pioneers a solution specifically dealing with the complexity of high-payload robots, thus both overcoming existing limitations and ensuring enhanced safety.

3. Requirements and contact model

3.1. General HRC safety system requirements

Safety functions in HRC focus on operator protection from potential hazards. Derived from risk assessment (please refer to [Appendix A - Terminology](#)), these functions consider robot velocity, distance, and force limitations, in line with ISO standards like ISO 10218-1, ISO 10218-2, ISO 13855:2010, and ISO/TS 15066. Adhering to EN ISO 10218-1, safety systems should match performance level (PL) "d" and structure category "3" as per ISO 13849-1 (please refer to [Appendix A - Terminology](#)), ensuring faults are detected and addressed without compromising safety. Close-proximity HRC applications demand increased safety attention.

In close-proximity Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC), attention is vital to minimize potential physical injury, complying with ISO 15066 standards for power and force limitations during both intentional and unintentional contacts. Robotic systems utilize passive and active safety design methods, like protective padding and contact sensing, to keep hazards below threshold limit values, respecting biomechanical limits set by ISO 15066. Two categories of contact events are quasi-static and transient contact. The former involves prolonged force/pressure application, requiring careful design to avoid positioning fixed structures near the robot path. The latter, transient contact, concerns collisions in free space and mandates advanced protection measures, including contact-sensitive skins and safety inverters [18].

To comply with the HRC requirements, the proposed approach utilizes two different sensors, communicating through distinct channels, with separate controllers ensuring safety. Thus, a single fault of the components and parts shall not lead to a potential loss of the safety function.

3.2. Collision modelling for high payload robots

The linearized contact model used here is introduced in [Fig. 1](#), where the robot has input of motor torque τ_m , measurements of robot joint and end-effector pose q , x and 6-DOF force/torque measurements F . The robot is coupled to the payload with a stiffness K_p , and there is a contact stiffness K_c which can model, e.g., a compliant covering. This system then interacts with the environment, through a human stiffness K_h , which is between either the human inertia or a 2nd force/torque sensor. In a clamped collision, the human inertia is also constrained by an environment stiffness K_e . The test environment here approximates the clamped contact conditions, which results in higher peak and quasistatic forces [17,19]. This model is applied in [Section 4.3](#) for the design of the collision detection algorithm.

4. Design of the collision detection system

4.1. Collision detection hardware system

To deal with the fact that F/T sensors frequently don't have the category "3" certification, the proposed method achieves redundant collision detection using two different sensors, an F/T sensor mounted at the end effector and values of current of axis motors. The data are shared through different communication pipelines with different network

Fig. 1. Model of robot, payload, and contact conditions; measured variables are marked in red.

connections and the safety function is enacted by two separate controllers after the evaluation for a potential collision has been performed. The described architecture structure is depicted in Fig. 2.

Based on the architecture described above, a F/T sensor placed on the flange of the robot measures the applied loads. The tool of the robot is placed on it. An amplifier captures the signals from the strain gauges and converts them to a higher amplitude electrical signal. The amplifier is connected via ETHERCAT fieldbus to an Automation PC (APC) where the data are afterwards provided to robotic system's ROS network at 1000 Hz. A ROS driver was implemented to share within the ROS network the robot motor current values at 500 Hz.

An additional driver was developed that connects the safety PLCs, to the ROS network using a dual channel TCP/IP – UDP connection, combining the more reliable nature of the first with the faster nature of the latter, to share the collision detection results from ROS. In case an error or data mismatching is detected by the two pipelines, a safety stop is triggered. The two PLCs (PILZ PSS4000 – Siemens S7 1500F) have a hardwire safe connection, which is used to guarantee that the data received from ROS are intact; otherwise, a safety stop is triggered. The S7 1500F PLC is connected to the X20 B&R safety system of the

collaborative robot and performs the emergency stop function, using PROFISAFE safety fieldbus.

4.2. Collision detection algorithm

The collision detector uses a model-free filtering with a threshold for both motor current and force/torque input data. A 2nd order Butterworth bandpass filter is applied with specified cutoff frequencies ω_l, ω_h ,

$$B_c = \frac{s^2 \omega_l^{-2}}{(s^2 \omega_l^{-2} + \sqrt{2} s \omega_l^{-1} + 1)(s^2 \omega_h^{-2} + \sqrt{2} s \omega_h^{-1} + 1)}$$

where, s is the Laplace variable. This transfer function is then discretized with the bilinear transform to give $B(z)$, where z is the Z-transform variable. This filter allows the removal of low-frequency signal (e.g., unmodelled gravitational forces) and suppression of high-frequency noise (e.g., white sensor noise).

The signals can also be pre-processed with numeric differentiations of 1st order $D(z) = f_s - f_s z^{-1}$, where f_s is the sample time. This increases the noise in the signal but improves the edge detection. For each DOF in

Fig. 2. System architecture.

the force or current measurement, the filter is applied independently as

$$\bar{F}_t^i = B(z)D(z)F_t^i \quad (1)$$

and independent DOF are combined with a weighting,

$$\alpha_t = \sum_i \beta_i \bar{F}_t^i, \quad (2)$$

where, β_i is a weighting coefficient and a collision is detected when $\alpha_t \geq \bar{\alpha}$. The parameters are published in ROS, where they are read into the collision detection node on start and used for monitoring.

4.3. Design of collision detector parameters

The time needed to detect contact will here be analyzed using a 1-DOF linear model as introduced in Fig. 1, where we consider the effects of signal differentiation and a payload inertia.

4.3.1. Differentiation of force signal

To improve the collision detection, a differentiation of the force signal can amplify the high-frequency content in sharp contacts. To analyze this, consider measurement signal $F = K_p(x - x_p)$, where x_p is constant (e.g. fixed by an infinite stiffness environment). If the robot is entering contact with a constant velocity v , and a collision is triggered when a threshold $\bar{\alpha}$ is exceeded, the collision will be detected with delay:

$$t_{det} = \frac{\bar{\alpha}}{vK_p} \quad (3)$$

When the force signal is differentiated and low-pass filtered, we have the processed signal $\bar{F} = \frac{s\omega_h}{s+\omega_h} F$, where s is the Laplace transform variable, equivalently in time domain

$$\dot{\bar{F}} = -\omega_h \bar{F} + \omega_h K_p v, \quad (4)$$

where, the fact that $\dot{F} = K_p v$ is used. This can be integrated and solved for when $\bar{F} = \bar{\alpha}$ as:

$$\bar{F}(t) = e^{-\omega_h t} \omega_h K_p v, \quad (5)$$

$$t_{det}^d = \omega_h^{-1} \ln \frac{\bar{\alpha}}{\omega_h K_p v}. \quad (6)$$

From this, we note that as ω_h decreases (i.e. the low-pass filter cutoff is reduced), the detection time increases. For values of ω_h used in the hardware setup here (90 rad/s), the detection time is significantly improved. Additionally, a lower stiffness K_p slows the detection of contact, as shown in more general settings [19].

4.3.2. Effects of payload on detection time

One challenge from an increased payload is the effect on detection time. To understand this, we consider the payload can be considered as a physical low-pass filter, where (without any acceleration of the robot, i.e. $\ddot{x} = 0$) the external force F_e induces measured force F as

$$F = \frac{K_p}{Ps^2 + B_p s + K_p} F_e \quad (7)$$

with effective cutoff frequency of $\omega_p = (K_p P^{-1})^{1/2}$, payload stiffness and damping values K_p , B_p from the model in Fig. 1. This cutoff frequency decreases as the payload mass P increases and increases as the stiffness K_p increases.

The low-pass filter acts similarly to a time delay, although the effective delay varies by frequency and thus depends on the frequency characteristics of the input signal. Using the results of the low-pass filter in Eq. (6), we can see increasing the payload increases the detection time.

4.3.3. Selection of detector parameters

To select the bandpass cutoffs, data is collected from the robot in motion with and without external collisions. The frequency domain is then compared between the two, as can be seen in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the oscillation of the payload around 22 Hz is present both with and without collision. The upper cutoff of the filter ω_h is set below 22 Hz to prevent oscillation being recognized as a collision. Near 0 Hz, the gravitational errors in the model can be seen. The major distinction between the two occurs between 4 and 8 Hz, so the lower cutoff ω_l should be below 4 Hz.

The collision thresholds can then be determined by tuning on offline data where the external F/T sensor indicates true collisions to find a balance of sensitivity and false positives.

5. Validation of collision detection method

5.1. Solar thermal collectors' assembly – use case

The proposed approach was examined with a use case derived from the renewable energy field. The first commercial High Payload Collaborative Robot (HPCR) COMAU AURA (payload 170 kg) was utilized for picking, manipulating, holding, and releasing a solar thermal collector. The HPCR, performs the strenuous task of holding the solar collector ($\sim 2200 \times 1200$ [mm]) weighing approximately from 35 kg, presenting it to the operator in the most convenient manner, thus letting the operator to execute the tasks that require dexterity (installation of smaller components like rivets, caps, stickers etc.) for the assembly completion.

An external sensorized foam skin, as part of the robot itself, can detect any kind of collision of the robot structure with the environment. The safety function performed by the sensorized system in case of momentary contact is a category 2 stop. If contact persists, then it performs a category 1 stop (please refer to Appendix A – Terminology for more information regarding safety stop categories).

5.2. End effector description

The end effector consists of an aluminum profile-based frame and pneumatic suction cups with the necessary valves. The suction cups are placed on spring-loaded compensators. The weight of the gripper is ~ 15 kg. A F/T sensor is placed between the profile frame and the flange of the robot, also used for hand guiding. The complexity of the robotic tool, its large dimensions, and the dimensions of the attached panel compels the rejection of a gripper covering solution using pressure sensitive foam pads.

5.3. Experimental setup

The experimental setup consists of an external F/T sensor, which was placed on a fixed structure constructed from aluminum profiles. The external F/T sensor was positioned on the fixture with a 3D printed base,

Fig. 3. Force/Torque signal in frequency domain, with and without collision.

which enabled the easy repositioning of the sensor for measuring both lateral and vertical collisions. The external F/T sensor had also integrated compliance of 16 N/mm to approximate the human stiffnesses. The effective spring constants for different parts of the human body are provided by the Annex A of ISO/TS 15066 [8], ranging from 10 to 150 N/mm. The value of 16 N/mm is between the stiffness for abdomen and pelvis, and is selected at the lower range because the rigidly fixed collision device provides collision forces roughly twice as large as a moveable inertia, i.e. a mass on a pendulum or linear rail [23]. A lower stiffness on a fixed mount thus allows safe tests with a simpler mechanical setup, and analytical methods can be used to translate these results to free-space collisions [24].

A lower stiffness also means that the maximum energy transfer will be achieved, as given in Eq. (8). In Eq. (8), E represents transfer energy, F_{\max} represents the maximum contact force, P_{\max} represents the maximum contact pressure for specific body region, K the effective spring constant (human body stiffness) and A represents the area of contact between robot and body region.

$$E = \frac{F_{\max}}{2K} = \frac{A^2 P_{\max}^2}{2K} \quad (8)$$

The setup is presented in Fig. 4.

The robot is driven by the jogging function into collision with the external F/T sensor. Different scenarios, varying in the approach velocity, robot extensions/poses, collision orientation, with/without the solar collector attached, and category stop (0–1) where implemented.

The data from the F/T sensors values (external and end effector), robot joint's currents, robot pose (end effector Cartesian and joints rotations), filtered signals etc. were all shared via the ROS framework, thus easing the data collection and processing actions.

5.4. Experimental results

In this section the experimental results are presented. The experiment data is available at Zenodo [20]. Unless otherwise noted, the values in Table 1 are used, empirically tuned from experiments.

The addition of a larger payload introduces resonance between the payload and force-torque sensor due to the effective stiffness between. When the panel is moving in the Z-direction of TCP (Fig. 6, right), where the EE is more compliant due to the suction grippers, there is a substantial internal peak which is much higher than external force. There is

Table 1
Collision detection parameters.

Detector	Cutoff freq. ω_l, ω_h (rad/s)	Threshold $\bar{\alpha}$	Weighting β
End-effector	(0.5, 90)	475	[1,1,1,0,0,0]
Joint current	(0.1, 150)	30	[0.5, 0.3, 1, 3, 6, 6]

also a substantial phase delay due to the payload, which can be seen in Fig. 5.

This means that the measurement of the flange F/T sensor ('Robot Forces') does not correspond to external forces applied ('External Forces'), with peaks of 540 and 260 N, respectively. The oscillation here has a dominant frequency of roughly 7 Hz, within typical human input ranges [14], which makes separating internal oscillation and human forces difficult.

A range of comparisons were then made to study the effect of individual parameters: robot elbow extension, motor torque vs F/T sensor, direction of motion, and emergency stop category. Each experiment is repeated three times, and average values from the trials are reported in Table 2. The results can also be seen in the attached video.

5.4.1. Elbow extension

The effect of robot elbow extension is validated by moving the end-effector closer or farther from the robot base, while keeping all other parameters the same, with the results seen in the Table 2. In longer extension, the collision detection demonstrated higher external peak force and steady state forces, which is expected as a result of the higher inertia. Also, both the detection and the stopping time presented higher delays in the longer extensions.

5.4.2. Motor current vs F/T sensor

Using the joint motor currents provides a secondary detection channel but has a slower response than the end-effector F/T sensor. This is compared, at a medium extension, with all parameters held the same. The EE measurements provide a reduction in average peak force of 41 N and average steady-state force of 34 N. The EE F/T sensor is closer to the collision (the collision forces have to pass through less inertia) and the EE parameters can be set more aggressively as there is no high-frequency signal coming from the position control of the robot.

Fig. 4. Experimental setup for collision measurements.

Fig. 5. Data visualization for a collision event. In Fig. 5.A, the whole plot is presented, and in Fig. 5.B there is a focus between contact event until max force to clearly distinct the detected collision from the two methods.

Table 2

Experiments results, all values are average over 3 trials.

Description	External Peak force (N)	Steady-state force (N)	Full stop duration (ms)	Detect time (ms)	Displacement (mm)
Robot extension (125 mm/s) – Long/Short					
Long	166	79	143	27	–
Short	117	97	49	0	–
Sensor (125 mm/sec) Joint/End-Effector F/T (EE)					
Joint	210	154	–	36	–
EE	169	120	–	28	–
Direction of motion (187.5 mm/s speed) – Vertical/Horizontal					
Vert	251	154	151	–	12.5
Horiz	197	80	147	–	15
End-effector stiffness (187.5 mm/s speed)					
Low stiff (Z)	148	103	–	33.6	–
High stiff (X)	269	163	–	31.3	–
Category stop (125 mm/s speed) – Cat0/Cat1					
Cat0	113	82	139	–	8
Cat1	129	93	150	–	9
Category stop (187.5 mm/s speed) – Cat0/Cat1					
Cat0	168	121	135	–	12
Cat1	168	119	131	–	12

5.4.3. Direction of motion

The effect of moving vertically or horizontally in world coordinates was compared by mounting the F/T sensor on the ground (vertical) and on a table in a horizontal orientation (horizontal), tested at a similar robot extension and keeping all other parameters the same. The horizontal motion shows a slightly lower peak and steady-state force value.

5.4.4. End-effector stiffness

The end-effector presents different stiffness in the Z direction (Fig. 6, right), where spring-loaded level compensators for the suction caps are oriented, compared to the other directions. Two experiments are compared with the panel contacting in the Z-direction vs in the X-direction of the TCP, realized by changing the orientation of the EE and keeping the same speed, robot extension from its base and detector

Fig. 6. Two contact trials with the panel, (left) with longer extension of the robot and (right) making contact in the direction of the suction gripper compliance.

Table 3

Offline detection comparison results.

	Detection time (ms)	
<i>Signal differentiation</i>	150 mm/s	187.5 mm/s
No differentiation	46.6	30.6
Differentiation	36.1	25.1
<i>Payload</i>		
No payload	50.8	61.8
Payload	43.6	38.2

parameters. It can be seen that the lower stiffness significantly reduces the peak and steady-state forces, even though slightly increasing detection time.

5.4.5. Safety category

Regarding the safety stops categories, as per the manufacturer, in category 0 stop, “stop performed without deceleration ramp”, while in category 1, “stop is performed with a steep deceleration ramp”. For contact speed of 125 mm/s, external peak force, steady-state force, stopping time, and stopping distance are higher in the category 1 stop. For higher speed (187.5 mm/s) the category stop did not have a great impact compared to lower speeds.

5.5. Offline validation of payload and differentiation

To compare the impact of various parameters, offline experiments are conducted by playing back the recorded data files of certain experiments to allow direct comparison of the time to detect contact (Table 3).

Signal differentiation improves the detection time by an average of 8 ms, which leads to an improved stopping distance of 1.2 mm at 150 mm/sec. This 1.2 mm results in a 48 N difference in steady-state force for a 40 N/mm environment, which can be substantial.

To compare the effects of payload, the same detector parameters are applied on a data with and without payload. Surprisingly, adding the panel results in a reduction of the detection time. This can be attributed to the fact that the no payload contact condition was with the compliant end-effector (Fig. 6, right). The compliance of the end-effector dominated the effect of the inertia, leading to increased contact detection times.

5.6. Industrial validation

To identify the benefits of the power and force limiting vs the speed and separation monitoring method in high payload collaborative applications, additional experiments were carried out in an industrial scenario. First, the presented collision detection was validated with a PILZ PRMS [22] device to find if it complied with the ISO/TS 15066 bio-mechanical limits. PILZ PRMS device measures force and pressure values in collision event experiments performed with the robot. It has springs and sensors to measure force, with nine springs simulating different human body regions. For pressure, it uses films to measure local pressure against standard limits. Additionally, a software tool helps in validating, digitalizing measurements, and generating reports. Indicative spring stiffness values used were $K = 150$ N/mm representing collisions with the skull and forehead, 75 N/mm and 50 N/mm representing collisions with the face and neck, and 25 N/mm and 10 N/mm and 35 N/mm representing collisions with the chest, abdomen and back/shoulders respectively.

During testing impact with the human skull was exceeding the limits provided by ISO/TS15066, especially the pressure limits, robot motions were limited for areas that did not pose any danger for collision with the human head. While head collision limits could not be held, the use-case could be adapted to avoid this scenario. This was monitored by the safety software of the robot that would not move the robotic gripper above human shoulders.

5 operators with varying manufacturing experience (1–5 years) and age (21–38 years) performed the assembly of the solar thermal collector using the collaborative robotic cell, altering between the two safety methods (4 iterations per method each). For speed and separation monitoring method, a certified 3D camera placed on the ceiling of the shopfloor in combination with a laser scanner was used.

The average cycle time using the power and force limiting was ~ 311 s while using the speed and separation monitoring was ~ 334 s. Although the maximum speed of the robot was the same in all the experiments, in case of the speed and separation monitoring experiments the operators had to step out of the dangerous zones prior the execution of a robot motion. Moreover, there were instances where another colleague from the factory violated the dangerous zones by mistake and additional motion reset procedure had to be followed by the operator. These resulted in increased cycle time ($\sim 7\%$) due to additional non-added value activities, while having negative impact on the fluidity of the collaboration. While the high payload collaborative application was perceived positively, especially regarding the reduction of physical

Fig. 7. Collision detection during a process cycle. When the operator hits the robot the robot indicator changes from green (a) to red (b) (emergency stop).

Table 4
Summary of important parameters and their impact on the collision detector.

Description	Change	Detect time	Stop time	Peak force
Robot extension	Increase	o	+	+
Direction of motion	Direction	o	o	o
Stop category	Cat1 to Cat0	o	-	-
Collision signal	EE to Joint	++	o	++

strain “lifting it 100, 150 times per day adds up towards the end of the day”, one operator noted for the speed and separation monitoring experiments “it would make me nervous to have to step outside and wait for the robot to finish” (Fig. 7).

6. Conclusion and outlook

This paper presented the implementation and validation of collision detection on high-payload manipulators using a F/T sensor on the robot flange as well as the robot motor currents.

Important parameters are summarized on Table 4 where a ‘+’ indicates positive effect, ‘-’ a negative effect, and ‘o’ no effect and the number indicates strength of effect. A bandpass filter plus differentiation was shown to be an easy and effective basis for the collision detection, reducing the effect of low-frequency signal (e.g., gravity terms) and high-frequency noise.

An experimental analysis at an industrial scenario showed the advantage of power and force limiting over speed and separation monitoring, both in terms of cycle time and psychological impact. Finetuning of the collision detection model parameters based on the application needs, would unveil the maximum performance.

For future work, the proposed implementation could be enhanced by lowering the time delays due to the data sharing. The robot controller and the F/T sensor could be directly connected to the safety PLC to evaluate the data and finally perform the safety functions if required. Additionally, the collision detection could be performed by using state of the art GPU modules that run on PLCs, to estimate potential collisions using neural networks supporting the presented solution. Finally, an extensive validation of the collision method could be done, by also evaluating pressure values.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Konstantinos Katsampiris-Salgado: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Kevin Haninger:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Christos Gkrizis:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation,

Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Nikos Dimitropoulos:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jörg Krüger:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **George Michalos:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Sotiris Makris:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Terminology

Risk assessment

Risk assessment is a systematic process for identifying hazards, estimating risks, and determining the appropriate safety measures to mitigate those risks. Risk assessment is mandatory for ensuring that machinery and processes are designed, operated, and maintained in a way that minimizes the risk, thus ensuring safety to human operators.

For more details the reader can refer to the directive ISO 12100:2010¹.

¹ ISO, Safety of machinery - General principles for design - Risk assessment and risk reduction (ISO 12100:2010), International Organization for Standardization, 2010.

Stop functions

The stop functions categorized as Category 0, Category 1, and Category 2 are part of machine safety standards, specifically related to the stopping of machinery in a way that ensures the safety of the operator and the machine itself. These categories define the methods and performance required for bringing machinery to a safe stop condition.

- **Category 0:** An uncontrolled stop where power to the machine actuators is immediately disconnected. This type of stop is generally considered the least safe as it doesn't account for any ongoing processes within the machinery.
- **Category 1:** A controlled stop with power available to the machine actuators until the machine reaches a safe condition, after which the power is disconnected.
- **Category 2:** A controlled stop with power left connected to the machine actuators. This allows the machine to be restarted by simply reactivating the machine controls.

For more details the reader can refer to the directives IEC 61800-5-2² and ISO 13850:2015³.

Performance Level (PL)

The term "Performance Level" refers to the level of reliability required for a safety-related function. In other words, it describes the ability of the safety function to minimize or eliminate the risk of harm effectively. The standard (ISO 13849-1) defines five performance levels: PL a, PL b, PL c, PL d, and PL e, with "PL e" being the highest level of safety. To estimate the PL, factors such as component lifespan (MTTFD), diagnostic coverage (DC), common cause failure (CCF), system structure, fault behavior, safety software, systematic failure, and environmental conditions should be considered. For more info the reader can refer to the directive ISO 13849-1:2023⁴.

Category (Cat.)

The term "Category" (often abbreviated as "Cat") in the context of ISO 13849-1 refers to the architectural structure and fault tolerance of safety-related parts of control systems. The category describes the ability of a system to withstand and/or detect failures while still performing its safety function. A concise overview of the categories according to ISO 13849-1 follows:

- Cat. B: Basic safety circuits, no diagnostic features.
- Cat. 1: Same as Cat B, but with minimal fault detection. No guarantee of preventing hazardous events.
- Cat. 2: Fault detection present. Signals faults but may not prevent hazardous events.
- Cat. 3: Redundant channels for better fault tolerance, but not all types of faults are detected.
- Cat. 4: Redundant channels with continuous cross-monitoring. Stops machine upon single fault detection.

For more info the reader can refer to the directive ISO 13849-1:2023.

² IEC, Adjustable speed electrical power drive systems - Part 5-2: Safety requirements - Functional (IEC 61800-5-2), International Electrotechnical Commission, 2016.

³ ISO, Safety of machinery - Emergency stop function - Principles for design (ISO 13850:2015), International Organization for Standardization, 2015.

⁴ ISO, Safety of machinery - Safety-related parts of control systems - Part 1: General principles for design (ISO 13849-1:2023), International Organization for Standardization, 2023.

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